

SHORT NOTES

Alkaloids from *Aconitum Palmatum* Don.

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The chemical study of the roots of *Aconitum palmatum* Don., obtained from the dealers under the name 'Vakhma', reveals the presence of a large number of alkaloids, from which five diterpene alkaloids have been isolated and characterised. This report is in continuation of an earlier report¹ on *Delphinium denudatum*.

Water-insoluble base, named Vakognavine (analyses fitting $C_{35}H_{41}O_{10}N$, m.p. 298°) yielded crystalline hydroiodide, $C_{35}H_{41}O_{10}N.HI.2\frac{1}{2}H_2O$, m.p. 235-37°; hydrochloride, $C_{35}H_{41}O_{10}N.HCl.H_2O$, m.p. 285°; hydrobromide, $C_{35}H_{41}O_{10}N.HBr.2\frac{1}{2}H_2O$, m.p. 251-52°; reineckate, $C_{35}H_{41}O_{10}N.H[(NH_3)_2.Cr(CNS)_4].2H_2O$, m.p. 215°(d); acetate, $C_{35}H_{41}O_{10}N.CO.CH_3.\frac{1}{2}H_2O$, m.p. 285-87°; picrolonate, $C_{35}H_{41}O_{10}N.C_{10}H_9O_5N_4.2H_2O$, m.p. 200-203°(d); and picrate, $C_{35}H_{41}O_{10}N.C_6H_3O_7N_3$, m.p. 185°(d). Group estimations indicate the presence of four ester groups, one of which is benzoate, as benzoic acid has been confirmed as one of the products of hydrolysis and the other three appear to be acetate groups, one *N*-alkyl group, and no *O*-alkyl group. Number of C-Me groups was not conclusive as the ester groups interfered in its estimation. The IR spectrum of the alkaloid in KCl disc showed bands at 2941, 1660, 909 cm^{-1} ($>C=CH_2$); multicarbonyl bands at 1695 to 1754 cm^{-1} (R-CO-O- and $>C=O$); 1282, 1250, 714 cm^{-1} (aromatic ring); 1115 cm^{-1} (O-C-N?); 2858 cm^{-1} (N-R); and 1375, 1441 cm^{-1} (C-CH₃).

The UV spectrum (methanol) showed λ_{max} 232 $m\mu$ (log ϵ , 4.1767). The evidence for the presence of a hydroxyl group is not conclusive. Estimation of active hydrogen in anisole gave negative results. Vakognavine thus appears to be an atisine base in which allylic hydroxyl has been oxidised to yield an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone. The IR spectrum of the hydroiodide salt indicated that the alkaloid isomerised with the elimination of double bond of the exomethylene group. Titration equivalent in acetic acid with perchloric acid was found to be 635 (potentiometric titration).

The ether-soluble alkaloid appears to be the palmatisine of Henry and Dunstan² though it had not been formulated before the name palmatisine is given to this alkaloid; its analyses correspond to $C_{22}H_{25}O_6N$ or $C_{24}H_{27}O_7N$, m.p. 285-86°. It yielded crystalline picrate, m.p. 164°, reineckate, m.p. 202°(d), and auric chloride complex, m.p. 220-25°. Group estimations indicated the presence of one active hydrogen, one *N*-alkyl group, two C-Me and no *O*-Me. The higher value of C-Me may be accounted for by the presence of an acetate group which has not been confirmed yet or by the presence of *N*.Et. The IR spectrum in KCl disc showed bands at 2941, 1660, 909 cm^{-1} ($>C=CH_2$); 3448 cm^{-1}

1. Singh *et al.*, *Chem & Ind.*, 1961, 1909.

2. Henry, "The Plant Alkaloids", Churchill Ltd., London, 1949, p. 674; *Bull. Imp. Inst.*, 1906, 4, 38.

(OH); 1754, 1740, 1710, 1695, 1661 cm^{-1} (multicarbonyl groups); 1449, 1362 cm^{-1} (C-CH₃). The UV spectrum (alcohol) showed λ_{max} 230 $\text{m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.973) and λ_{max} 206 $\text{m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.745). Palmatisine therefore appears to be a diterpene alkaloid with allylic group present as an α - β -unsaturated ketone and having multicarbonyl groups.

The chloroform-soluble alkaloid has been named, Vakatisine. Its analyses correspond to C₂₂H₂₃O₄N, m.p. 306°. It yielded crystalline hydrochloride, m.p. 251°; hydroiodide, m.p. 256-57°; triacetate, m.p. 233-34°; picrate, m.p. 146°(d); and perchlorate, m.p. 253-55°. Group estimations indicated the presence of one C-Me, one *N*-alkyl, and no *O*-Me in the base and three acetyl groups in triacetate. Active hydrogen could not be estimated as the compound was not soluble in any suitable solvent; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} + 17.76$ (EtOH). The alkaloid was found to be a very weak base and could not be titrated in aqueous and non-aqueous media. The IR spectrum indicated the presence of bands at 2941, 1653, 891 cm^{-1} ($>\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$); 1675 cm^{-1} ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$); 1447, 2874 cm^{-1} (C-CH₃); 3413, 3289 cm^{-1} (OH). The UV spectrum (EtOH) showed λ_{max} 207 $\text{m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.8462). The carbonyl group appears to be in the close vicinity of the nitrogen atom, exercising a pull on the lone pair of N-electrons. This may account for the low value of band absorption in the IR and the low basicity of the alkaloid.

The two water soluble bases have been named Vakatisinine and Vakatidine respectively. Analysis of Vakatisinine corresponds to C₂₂H₃₃O₄N, m.p. 308°. It yielded crystalline picrolonate, m.p. 302° (d) and hydrochloride, m.p. 303°. The IR spectrum indicated the presence of bands at 2941, 1653, 893 cm^{-1} ($>\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$); 1685 cm^{-1} ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$); 1449, 2858 cm^{-1} (C-Me); 3448, 3280 cm^{-1} (OH). The UV spectrum (EtOH) showed λ_{max} 210 $\text{m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.8344).

Analysis of Vakatidine fits C₂₂H₃₃O₂N, m.p. 295-96°. It yielded crystalline hydrochloride, m.p. 304° and hydrobromide, m.p. 272-74°. The IR spectrum showed presence of bands at 2941, 1653, 893 cm^{-1} ($>\text{C}=\text{CH}_2$); 1685 cm^{-1} ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$); 1449, 2858 cm^{-1} (C-CH₃); 3448, 3280 cm^{-1} (OH). The UV spectrum (EtOH) showed λ_{max} 211 $\text{m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 3.6525).

Strip and circular paper chromatography showed that all the five alkaloids isolated were single compounds with the *R_f* values of 0.95 (Vakognavine), 0.79 (Palmatisine), 0.77 (Vakatisine), 0.80 (Vakatisinine), and 0.83 (Vakatidine) at 21° in *n*-butanol/citric acid/water system and Munier's reagent as developer.

Further work in relation to the elucidation of structural framework of the major alkaloids by selenium dehydrogenation, reductions, and oxidations of these alkaloids is in progress and will be reported shortly.